

A method for calling complex SVs

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This document describes methods used by the Human Genome Structural Variation Consortium (HGSC) to identify large, complex structural variants (SVs) using phased sequences. These methods are in development and will be integrated into a future release of PAV (Ebert et al. 2021).

Data

We utilized 65 phased assemblies (130 haplotypes) derived from 1000 Genomes samples that were generated by the Human Genome Structural Variation Consortium (HGSC). Briefly, the cell lines were sequenced with PacBio HiFi, Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT), and Strand-seq, and resulting data were used to produce near-T2T quality phased assemblies (**Manuscript in preparation**).

Genome references

Variant calls were performed against reference sequence T2T-CHM13v2.0 (T2T-CHM13) (Nurk et al. 2022).

Alignments

To produce a callset, each haplotype assembly is aligned to the reference genome with minimap2. Alignments are performed twice, once with a set of parameters for spanning large SVs (Tier-1) and another for filling in unaligned bases left unaligned by the first set of alignments (Tier-2).

Tier-1 alignments: The first set of parameters has been the default parameters since PAV's inception and was designed to span large structural variants (Vollger et al. 2020; Ebert et al. 2021). The command for this alignment is "minimap2 -x asm20 -m 10000 -z 10000,50 -r 50000 --end-bonus=100 -0 5,56 -E 4,1 -B 5 --secondary=no -a -t <threads> --eqx -Y <input> <reference>". Per haplotype, Tier-1 alignments yield 463 to 930 alignment records per haplotype (mean 637) after alignment-trimming in query space (see below) and has good coverage for large SVs, although smaller alignments and fragments of complex structures are left unaligned.

Tier-2 alignments: The second set of parameters was added to improve alignments for fragments of complex structures. The command for this alignment is "minimap2 -x asm20 --secondary=no -a -t <threads> --eqx -Y <input> <reference>" and yields 8,606 to 21,297 (mean 14,159) alignment records after alignment trimming in query space (see below).

Both tiered alignments are run for each haplotype (**Fig. 1**).

Alignment trimming

As outlined previously (Ebert et al. 2021), PAV does not allow any query (assembly) base to be aligned to more than one location, which is often produced by alignment tools in repetitive structures surrounding alignment-truncating SVs (SVs that fragment alignment records into multiple records).

The initial alignments produced by PAV (Trim-None) have no alignment trimming applied. PAV first trims in query space (Trim-Qry) such that no query base appears in more than one alignment record (i.e. each query base is aligned zero or one times). Briefly, PAV identifies any alignment records overlapping in query coordinates and eliminates redundancy using a simple trimming algorithm to choose a cut site between two overlapping alignment records maximizing the number of mismatches and gaps (insertions or deletions) removed by the cut operation. In the case of ambiguity with equally optimal cut sites, a cut-site is chosen to left-align the break in query space. Complex variant calls are derived from this set of alignments.

After trimming in query space, PAV performs a second round of trimming to remove redundancies in reference space (Trim-QryRef). These alignments are used for calling variants embedded within the alignments (i.e. inside alignment CIGAR strings) and for choosing the insertion site for large tandem duplications.

Joining alignment tiers

PAV reconciles the two alignments for each haplotype, one with contiguous alignments across large SVs (Tier-1), and one with alignments with sensitivity to smaller fragments (Tier-2). For both tiers, Trim-Qry alignments are joined. As with query trimming, PAV retains Tier-2 alignments mapping query bases that are not aligned by Tier-1. For Tier-2 alignment records overlapping in Tier-1 in query space, the Tier-2 alignment is trimmed until all redundancies are removed retaining only the Tier-2 fragments not mapped in Tier-1. If there are no aligned bases in a Tier-2 alignment after trimming against Tier-1, the Tier-2 record is discarded.

Alignment truncating variants

Introduction. While smaller SVs may be embedded within alignment records (i.e. CIGAR strings), large SVs break alignments into multiple records near SV breakpoints. These SVs can have simple or complex structures, and they can be identified by tracing the query sequence through the alignment records on query-trimmed alignments (Trim-Qry). PAV requires all alignment-truncating variants to be anchored on each end with an SV sequence between anchors (**Fig. 2**).

When considering complex SVs, choosing anchors is not trivial. For example, a complex deletion with a small aligned fragment in the middle could be two simple deletions or a complex deletion with a small templated insertion in the middle (**Fig. 2, complex deletion**). In this case, PAV will need to consider both representations (two simple deletions or one complex deletion) and choose the best one.

Alignments often contain small complexities at breakpoints leading to ambiguity in the correct SV structure. Anchoring alignments for most insertions will meet at the same base (i.e. the left anchor ends at one base, and the right anchor begins at the next base), although small complexities at the breakpoints often occur. In these cases, a reasonable model should call these as simple variants (e.g. insertion, deletion, or inversion) allowing for small insertions or deletions at the breakpoint. If the complexities become significant, then a complex variant call should be made instead of a simple variant call. To guide this choice, PAV scores each SV using a scoring model and chooses the best representation for the variant.

Choosing anchor pairs and scoring SVs between them are tightly-coupled in PAV's algorithm. To find the best variant calls, PAV builds a graph of anchor candidates, calls and scores variants between anchors, and uses the variant and alignment scores to choose the best path and therefore the optimal variant calls through the graph structure. This process is completed for each query of each haplotype independently of all other query sequences.

Score model. A multi-segment affine score model is implemented with default parameters matching minimap2 (Li 2018) default double-affine parameters. This model scores matches, mismatches, and gaps (insertions and deletions) using gap-open and gap-extend penalties for alignments and variant calls. PAV's implementation accepts any number of gap-open/gap-extend pairs (multi-segment affine), and when scoring gaps, will try all and choose the lowest penalty. An additional penalty is added for template switches to support complex variant calls, which by default is set to the cost of two 50 bp gaps under the affine parameters.

To apply these scores to alignments and variants, we define score constants R and a score function $score(o, l)$ taking an operation code (o) and an operation length (l) and returning the score for that operation. Operation codes are defined as relevant CIGAR string operators (ignoring clipping and padding operations) with an additional element for template switches ($o = \text{\textit{i}}$), which has no representation in CIGAR strings. For convenience, we define $gap(l)$ as the cost of a gap (insertion or deletion) of length l .

$R_m :=$ Alignment match score : $R_m > 0$
 $R_x :=$ Alignment mismatch score : $R_x < 0$
 $R_o :=$ Gap open score : $R_o < 0$
 $R_e :=$ Gap extend score : $R_e < 0$
 $R_t :=$ Template switch score : $R_t < 0$

$$gap(l) = R_o + R_e \times l$$

$$score(o, l) = \begin{cases} l \times R_m : o = \mathbf{m} \\ l \times R_x : o = \mathbf{o} \\ gap(l) : o \in \{\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{d}\} \\ t : o = \mathbf{t} \end{cases}$$

Input. A score model, query-trimmed (Trim-Qry) alignment records, and reference-trimmed alignments (Trim-QryRef) are input into the large variant detection algorithm. Each alignment record is scored by summing the score for all alignment events within the alignment record using records in the CIGAR string ($S(a_i)$). For convenience, we define $cigar(a_i)$ as a function that returns tuples of CIGAR operation codes and lengths for alignment a_i .

$A :=$ Set of alignments for one query ordered in query coordinates

$a_i :=$ Sequence alignment record i in A ($a_i \in A$)

$$S(a_i) = \sum_{o,l}^{cigar(a_i)} score(o, l)$$

Anchor candidates. Large variants are anchored on each side by alignment records. These anchors are not part of the variant itself, but they set the breakpoints of simple variant or outer-most breakpoints for CPX variants. For example, a deletion has alignment records on both sides contiguous in query coordinates with unaligned reference sequence between them (**Fig. 2**). An anchor pair is derived from the same query sequence and must satisfy two criteria, they must be in the same aligned orientation on the same reference sequence, and they must have a sufficiently high-score to support a variant call between them. PAV identifies pairs of anchor candidates using an exhaustive search over all possible anchor pairs sufficiently close enough in query space to support a variant.

The following algorithm describes building a set of candidate anchor pairs (I).

$Q(i, j) :=$ The number of query bases between a_i and a_j
 $R(i, j) :=$ The number of reference bases from a_i and a_j (may be negative)
 $strand(x) :=$ Aligned strand of a_x .

Data: A

Result: $I :=$ Anchor intervals

$i \leftarrow 0$

while $i < |A| - 1$ **do**

$j \leftarrow i + 1$

while $gap(Q(i)) < S(a_i)$ **and** $j < |A|$ **do**

if $gap(Q(i)) < S(a_j)$ **and** $strand(i) = strand(j)$ **then**

$I \leftarrow I \cup \{(i, j)\}$

end

end

end

The resulting set of anchor pairs, I , defines intervals over the ordered set of alignments, A , that define candidate variants. Any element a_i of A may be an anchor or between anchors of many candidate intervals.

Variant calling. For every interval (i, j) in I , a candidate variant call is created and scored. We define $seg(i, j)$ as the number of non-anchor segments (aligned or unaligned) in the interval. The requirements for each variant type and the method for scoring each type of variant for a segment $(V_{i, j})$ is given below.

$G(i, j) :=$ An ordered set of segments between anchors i and j . Some may be unaligned

$G(i, j)_k :=$ A segment k in the ordered set $G(i, j)$ such that $0 \leq k < |G(i, j)|$

$len(G(i, j)_k) :=$ Length of segment k in $G(i, j)$

$V_{i,j} :=$ Score of the variant anchored at a_i and a_j

Insertions:

$$|G(i, j)| = 1$$

$$Q(i, j) > 0$$

$$V_{i,j} = gap(Q(i, j)) + gap(|R(i, j)|)$$

Deletions:

$$|G(i, j)| = 0$$

$$R(i, j) > 0$$

$$V_{i,j} = gap(R(i, j))$$

Tandem duplications:

$$|G(i, j)| = 0$$

$$R(i, j) < 0$$

$$V_{i,j} = gap(R(i, j))$$

Inversions:

$$|G(i, j)| = 1$$

$$strand(i + 1) \neq strand(i)$$

$$strand(i + 1) \in \{+, -\}$$

$$R(i, j) > 0$$

$$V_{i,j} = R_t \times 2 + gap(|R(i, j) - Q(i, j)|)$$

Complex:

$$|G(i, j)| \geq 1$$

$$V_{i,j} = R_t \times (|G(i, j)| + 1) + \sum_{k=0}^{|G(i, j)|-1} len(gap(G(i, j)_k))$$

Under this scoring scheme, different representations for the same variant between anchors i and j can be evaluated. For example, an inversion is penalized for a difference in the size of the inverted and aligned segment ($gap(|R(i, j) - Q(i, j)|)$), and if this difference is too large, then the score for a complex event would have a higher (less negative) score and become the chosen representation. This scheme allows for simple variant breakpoints to have some uncertainty or small complexities.

If no variant patterns exist for a pair of anchors, then the anchor pair is discarded.

Choosing optimal variants. From all variant candidates, an optimal set of variants must be chosen so that no variant overlap in query space. All alignment records may anchor up to two variants, one upstream and one downstream (in query coordinates), no query base may appear in more than one variant, and no query base may be part of both an anchor and a variant.

To choose the best set of variants, we construct a graph where all alignment records are vertices (V is the set of all vertices) and directional edges are created between vertices (E is the set of edges) such that traversing the graph strictly increases in query coordinates. The source node points to the first aligned segment, and the sink node is reached from the last. An edge is drawn between two nodes if there is a variant call between them. To connect the graph for traversal, adjacent edges are added between vertices adjacent in query coordinates (omitting unaligned sequence between them) if there is no variant call between the alignment anchors. The positive weight of each vertex is the positive score for the alignment record it represents. The negative weight of each edge is equivalent to the negative variant score it represents or is set to zero if the edge does not represent a variant call. The score of a path from source to any vertex is the sum of the score of all vertices and edges along the path. If neither edge going in and out of a vertex along the path, then the weight of the node is not added to the path. Omitting non-anchor alignment scores avoids biasing scores on small noisy alignment records.

This creates a directed acyclic graph (DAG) across all alignment records (nodes) and variants (edges) which can be solved efficiently with the Bellman-Ford algorithm ([DOI: 10.1090/qam/102435](https://doi.org/10.1090/qam/102435)). Conveniently, the DAG is already topologically because all paths are strictly increasing in query coordinates, which allows the graph to be solved in $O(|V| + |E|)$ time.

Figures

Figure 1. Alignment stages in PAV. PAV performs alignments in two tiers, one highly contiguous across SVs (Tier 1) and the other more sensitive to small, aligned fragments (Tier 2). Tiers are combined (Tier 0) and these alignments are used to identify small and large variants. Variant calling utilizes pre-trimmed alignments to identify failing variants likely to show up in other callsets.

Figure 2. Illustrations of how anchors function for large SV detection. Anchors (dark blue) after alignment trimming in query space (Trim-Qry) appear on each side of a large SV with segments of aligned or unaligned query sequence between anchors (red) and connections between them in assembly coordinates (black lines). PAV recognizes three types of simple SVs (left), deletions, insertions, inversions, and tandem duplications, each with a distinct alignment signature. For simple inversions, non-anchor query sequence (red) must be aligned in reverse orientation. All other variants fall into the complex category (right), which often have signatures resembling simple SVs. Not all simple variants will have exact breakpoints, for example an insertion with a small deletion-like gap at the breakpoint, and a scoring model is used to determine if these SVs fall into a simple SV category or the complex category.

Figure 3. Illustration of a variant graph. Each aligned segment (numbered circle) is a vertex in the graph connected by edges and has weight equal to the alignment score computed by PAV. Each vertex (arrow) connects edges where the edges are an anchor pair (black arrows) or adjacent without a variant (gray arrows). The highest-scoring traversal of the graph determines which variants are accepted.

References

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